

The Dark Matter Dine & Dash

Shopping around for answers; Dark Matter Scatter part 2

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February, 2019

ABSTRACT

Model failures are known to all, and the “crisis in Cosmology” continues to deepen. While some are embracing the plasma-electromagnetic (PEM) model and trying to hybridize the Standard Model further with incompatible elements, others make a mad dash to shop around for tools from other systems, or from pseudoscientific ideas, in order to give the semblance of scientific progress. But the dash to create a hybrid chimera of science, ignoring all mathematical and philosophical incompatibilities, can be erased with a shift into the Plasma-Electromagnetic Cosmologies, as has been discussed in previous parts. In describing the “scatter” of ideas, the chronology and *current* of thought remains the most pertinent discussion. In this paper, an examination of the latest failures in Accretion, Dark Matter (DM), and classical Black Holes reveals the continuing efforts of the mainstream/Big Bang school to hide the failures of gravitational-based models while simultaneously adapting PEM models, claiming they accepted them all along.

Keywords: Axion - Neutrino - Neutron Stars - Magnetic Current - Dark Matter - Black Holes

Updates on Dark Universe Search

In the last few weeks since the release of the “Dark Matter Scatter,” several new papers have come out that lay it out very clear that the mainstream Standard Model (SM) is desperate for solutions, and short on options:

Big Bang itself is undergoing a nip n’ tuck revisioning, whereby electricity is there... but gravity is sort of hiding the truth (folded, as it were), and it is perplexing cosmologists. ESA put out this article describing the conundrum,

“Investigating the history of our cosmos with a large sample of distant ‘active’ galaxies observed by ESA’s XMM-Newton, a team of astronomers found there might be more to the early expansion of the Universe than predicted by the standard model of cosmology...”

A new study, led by Guido Risaliti of Università di Firenze, Italy, and Elisabeta Lusso of Durham University, UK, points to another type of cosmic tracer – quasars – that would fill part of the gap between these observations, measuring the expansion of the Universe up to 12 billion years ago.

Quasars are the cores of galaxies where an active supermassive black hole is pulling in matter from its surroundings at very intense rates, shining brightly across the electromagnetic spectrum. As material falls onto the black hole, it forms a swirling disc that radiates in visible and ultraviolet light; this light, in turn, heats up nearby electrons, generating X-rays...

“When we combine the quasar sample, which spans almost 12 billion years of cosmic history, with the more local sample of type-Ia supernovas, covering only the past eight billion years or so, we find similar results in the overlapping epochs,” says Elisabeta.

*“However, in the earlier phases that we can only probe with quasars, **we find a discrepancy between the observed evolution of the Universe and what we would predict based on the standard cosmological model.**”*

“Looking into this previously poorly explored period of cosmic history with the help of quasars, the astronomers have revealed a possible tension in the standard model of cosmology, which might require the addition of extra parameters to reconcile the data with theory.

“One of the possible solutions would be to invoke an evolving dark energy, with a density that increases as time goes by,” says Guido.

Incidentally, this particular model would also alleviate another tension that has kept cosmologists busy lately, concerning the Hubble constant – the current rate of cosmic expansion. This discrepancy was found between estimates of the Hubble constant in the local Universe, based on supernova data – and, independently, on galaxy clusters – and those based on Planck’s observations of the cosmic microwave background in the early Universe.”¹ (emphasis added)

The author’s response to this hand-waving is quick, and concise:

1. There will always be more to the story. The fact that they have stated this shows how bad the hubris is in BBC/SM
2. Once again gravity is converted magically into reality. Black Holes are nebulae sized electric generators, of course they are releasing EMF in all spectrums.
3. This discrepancy is what is being glossed over. The Tension being spoken of is the “uh oh” moment that is quietly being swept under the rug.²

¹ http://www.esa.int/Our_Activities/Space_Science/Active_galaxies_point_to_new_physics_of_cosmic_expansion

² <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1901.05289.pdf>

4. Read “evolving dark energy” as “fudge factor” and understand that energy is work * time. It is literally what is exchanged by forces. It cannot evolve because it is not a biological organism.

Dear Reader, if the author were to come to you and assert that there were nargles in your car engine, and that’s why it makes noise, this would not square with what you know, or what a car mechanic would say. Now if the author insisted that the solution was to purchase were-bunnies to eat the nargles and place them in the engine compartment to resolve the “tension” between his theory and the mechanics, would you pay for it?

Why not? Because already B. Pandey has gone shopping for a solution, and with not too much difficulty found the ancient solution to the Dark Energy conundrum - the Void,

*“ABSTRACT We propose an alternative physical mechanism to explain the observed accelerated expansion of the Universe based on the configuration entropy of the cosmic web and its evolution. We show that the sheets, filaments and clusters in the cosmic web act as sinks whereas the voids act as the sources of information. The **differential entropy of the cosmic velocity field increases with time and also acts as a source of entropy**. The growth of non-linear structures and the emergence of the cosmic web may lead to a situation where the overall dissipation rate of information at the sinks are about to dominate the generation rate of information from the sources. Consequently, the Universe either requires a dispersal of the overdense non-linear structures or an accelerated expansion of the underdense voids to prevent a violation of the second law of thermodynamics. The dispersal of the sheets, filaments and clusters are not a viable option due to the attractive nature of gravity but the repulsive and outward peculiar gravitational acceleration at the voids makes it easier to stretch them at an accelerated rate. **We argue that this accelerated expansion of the voids inside the cosmic web may mimic the behaviour of dark energy.**”³ (emphasis added)*

The author doesn’t condone the ignoring of electrical mechanisms in plasma, especially the known convergences of plasma into filaments, sheets, and webs. But this sort of shopping around is condonable because it has a basis in something: previously discussed mechanisms empirically observed for thousands of years, and observation of the nonlinear dynamics of spatial network systems. This is how the Universe actually works. In the previous article, the author used the word “fall” like it was an accident. Somehow falling (ie, violating thermodynamics by performing work on itself in space), would convert a ridiculous amount of potential energy - with no description of its own source - into kinetic energy, which caused thermal radiation (of EMF waves). This is pure nonsense magic. Nothing is “falling,” it is being guided by a filamentary force field or fields if one wishes to divide into the 5 aspects⁴ of the single Dao of things.⁵

As for the concept in bold, this mirrors in almost exact meaning and conceptualization the author’s own “Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis,” introduced in a previous part⁶. As of the assertions made thereafter he may or may not agree, depending on how things turn out for Intrinsic Redshift (see Table 2) and the known distance failures of Doppler Redshift. But the final argument certainly jives with the assertions of Daoists, Brahmins, etc... who witnessed events that convinced them of the power of the Void (Shunyata/ Wuji), and of the existence of primordial chaotic “waters” (Hundun) which formed a soup of **visible** material... most reflected by the Baryonic hot grains in modern astrophysics.⁷

In the Dark Matter discussion, the COSINE-100 Collaboration has released their wimpy results in the search for WIMPs using sodium iodide detectors,

“We observe no excess of signal-like events above the expected background in the first 59.5

³ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1901.08475.pdf>

⁴ The “five phases of Force” we may term it.

⁵ Gravity, Magnetism, Di-Electricity, Electroweak, and Strong

⁶ [12] & [13]

⁷ [8]

days of data from COSINE-100. Assuming the so-called standard dark-matter halo model, this result rules out spin-independent WIMP–nucleon interactions as the cause of the annual modulation observed by the DAMA collaboration 20,21,22,23. The exclusion limit on the WIMP–sodium interaction cross-section is $1.14 \times 10^{-40} \text{ cm}^2$ for 10-GeV $c-2$ WIMPs at a 90% confidence level. The COSINE-100 experiment will continue to collect data for two more years, enabling a model-independent test of the annual modulation observed by the DAMA collaboration.”⁸

The author’s response is that they can search for two or two hundred more years, and they aren’t going to find WIMPs, because they do not exist - and he has a 99.9% confidence level of that.

That isn’t to say the experiment isn’t worthwhile. If one shows up to a deserted island there might be pirate treasure or there might not. But when you’d dug up the entire island, there will certainly be some type of use for the island. Is it worth the expense of resources? Depends on what natural treasures are dug up. After all, you might look for Spanish gold and find Mayan mica. It was valuable to someone, and so will these results be. But although the author applauds the elimination of false hypotheses, he does not condone creating weird hypotheses to acquire grants to simply knock down. This is the behavior of creating straw men, and is a logical fallacy.

Now is it fair to describe the situation thusly? The author thinks so, as daily (it seems) new places are being discovered which do not even need dark matter.^{9 10} Is that to be interpreted - as it has been despite the logical fallacy that it represents - as proof of DM existence? If again the island found has no Spanish gold is that proof one exists with the booty desired? Of course, not. But if one has evidence, such as a treasure map or a story of where a ship went down, etc... then it becomes slightly more reasonable. The story surrounding DM is as flimsy as the search for El Dorado. But while El Dorado has cost a few lives and fortunes, the search for DM has cost billions which could have been directly spent on the PEMC search and to further our understanding of a known and viable material. This material (plasma) is known to create crystalline, ultracold, ultrahot phases¹¹ as well as exist in four modes: darkened, glow, arc, and super-high-energy (Birkeland Current)¹². Wouldn’t it be better to simply try to understand Plasma-electromagnetism at all scales from quark to quasar? Of course, that would require being logical and frugal, and treating science as a method and not a free-for-all shopping spree.

It would require stellar cosmologists to stop inventing ways to use the wrong words¹³ to describe important PEM motion¹⁴, behavior (see Figure 1), forces, etc... and to even re-adopt classical, proven definitions for work, energy, power, etc... from geniuses such as Tesla, Steinmetz, and Heaviside¹⁵. It would require, in short: expertise in plasma-electromagnetic cosmology, and not in fantasy. But we have 40 years of fantasy scientists and scientologists doing mathemagics and guesswork, and they will not be stopping because of a pesky “can’t find it” issue. Instead they will, as predicted¹⁶, be making up new pseudo scientific words¹⁷ and browsing - buffet style - for any haphazard conglomeration to post. In the very new future they will invent new WIMP-like devices, dozens of them, and state that all of them must be tested, and any number of them (or none!) will be found. In an age where geology and meteorology^{18 19} are turning more and more to electricity

⁸ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-018-0739-1#change-history>

⁹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1901.05973.pdf>

¹⁰ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1901.04638.pdf>

¹¹ [11]

¹² [4]

¹³ Such as “jets” <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-019-00043-x>

¹⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1901.02747.pdf>

¹⁵ “A Common Language for Electrical Engineering: Lone Pine Writings, Volume 1,” E. Dollard, 2015

¹⁶ [8]

¹⁷ [12]

¹⁸ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364682618304541>

¹⁹ <https://www.newscientist.com/article/dn13669-shooting-clouds-with-lasers-triggers-electrical-discharge/>

(and magnetism²⁰), and black holes even are being turned electric (see below), how can astrophysical cosmogony do anything else?

Figure 1: Complete Solar Flare Eruption, with acceleration/deceleration along electromagnetic field gradients²¹

If anyone is keeping count, yes Dark Matter is still missing.²²

Two papers recently released, one from SENSEI and a more intriguing one from X. Hernandez detail continuing observational and logical problems for DM:

*“ABSTRACT We present new direct-detection constraints on eV-to-GeV dark matter interacting with electrons using a prototype detector of the Sub-Electron-Noise Skipper-CCD Experimental Instrument. The results are based on data taken in the MINOS cavern at the Fermi National Accelerator Laboratory. We focus on data obtained with two distinct readout strategies. For the first strategy, we read out the Skipper-CCD continuously, accumulating an exposure of 0.177 gram-days. While we **observe no events containing three or more electrons**, we find a large one- and two-electron background event rate, which we attribute to spurious events induced by the amplifier in the Skipper-CCD readout stage. For the second strategy, we take five sets of data in which we switch off all amplifiers while exposing the Skipper-CCD for 120k seconds, and then read out the data through the best prototype amplifier. ... **We again observe no events containing three or more electrons**, for an exposure of 0.069 gram-days. We use these data to derive world-leading constraints on dark matter-electron scattering for masses between 500 keV to 5 MeV, and on **dark-photon dark matter** being absorbed by electrons for a range of masses below 12.4 eV.”²³ (emphasis added)*

²⁰ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1901.04720.pdf>

²¹ <https://news.ucar.edu/132648/emergence-eruption> Image: Courtesy Mark Cheung, Lockheed Martin, and Matthias Rempel, NCAR

²² <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1901.03711.pdf>

²³ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1901.10478.pdf>

*“ABSTRACT Within the dark matter paradigm, explaining observed orbital dynamics at galactic level through the inclusion of a dominant dark halo, implies also the necessary appearance of dynamical friction effects. Satellite galaxies, globular clusters and even stars orbiting within these galactic halos, will perturb the equilibrium orbits of dark matter particles encountered, to produce a resulting trailing wake of slightly enhanced dark matter density associated with any perturber in the halo. The principal effect of this gravitational interaction between an orbiting body and the dark matter particles composing it, is the appearance of a frictional drag force slowly removing energy and angular momentum from the perturber. Whilst this effect might be relevant to help bring about the actual merger of the components of interacting forming galaxies, at smaller stellar scales, it becomes negligible. However, the trailing wake will still be present. In this letter I show that the corresponding dark matter wake associated to the Sun, will constitute a small but resonant perturbation on solar system dynamics which can be ruled out, as current laser and radio ranging measurements are now over an order of magnitude more precise than the amplitude of the orbital perturbations which said wake implies. The **absence of any such detection implies the nonexistence of the dynamical friction trailing wake on the sun, which in turn strongly disfavours dark matter as an explanation for the observed gravitational anomalies at galactic scales.**”²⁴ (emphasis added)*

The author’s responses are as follows:

1. Adding more and more constraints is generally a good process, but adding 100 constraints, or 1,000 will not matter if your basis is searching for pseudoscientific “dark photons.” World-leading, or not.
2. Hernandez does an excellent job here of describing in one paragraph the logic which should persist in the search for DM Haloes. Start with what you know, and can observe, and scale up from there. Astrophysics has taken entirely too much out on the plate at the buffet, and cannot even begin to swallow the scale of the problem. In the first place it’s a proposed substance, in the second now they are proposing how to measure the friction with plasma and ordinary matter, and it’s all completely speculative.

In response to this speculation, a previously cited author, W. Giordano has this to say,

“I firmly believe that when the volume of the universe is recomputed to reflect $2 \pi^2 r^3$ instead of $(4/3)(\pi r^3)$, the so called dark matter will prove to be a miscalculation of visible matter by the density difference factor coupled with unilluminated gas and dust²⁵... everyone is using the volume for a 3D ball for the universe. But, if it is a 4-ball the volume of the 3D outer volume is 4.71 times larger. [There was a report a few years ago that the UV light being received from the cosmos was off by a factor of 400%²⁶.]”²⁷

That may be speculation, but it is based on something observed, and is a plausible response to that observation!²⁸ Hernandez elaborates,

“[the list of failures] illustrates the increasing amount and variety of work going into developing ideas alternative to the dark matter paradigm. This has been partly in response to the various problems which have arisen with the standard picture in terms of details (e.g. Famaey & McGaugh 2012), but mostly, due to the continual and complete lack of a direct detection or an independent confirmation of the existence of dark matter, beyond gravitational anomalies in the low acceleration regime. Recently

²⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1901.10605.pdf>

²⁵ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1404.2933.pdf>

²⁶ <https://www.cnet.com/news/universes-missing-photons-baffle-scientists/>

²⁷ Emails dated 1/25/19 and 1/29/19

²⁸ https://www.academia.edu/27815784/On_the_Geometry_of_Our_Universe_Rev_Aug_15_2016

*we have seen all direct detection experiments **return only null results** (e.g. Yang 2016), as sensitivity limits previously deemed important have been reached and surpassed... The current dark matter paradigm is a framework where the driving causal entity is something which no one has ever seen a single particle of.*²⁹ (clarification added)

That pretty much sums the issue up.

Black Holes Die and Get a Face-lift

To start with, the reader must understand something: black holes as they were originally defined **do not exist** except in science-fiction³⁰. They have not proven General Relativity, because GR specifies and hypothesizes them to be a Singularity with a Schwarzschild radius of **0**. This means, a non-physical radius. These black holes are defined as being infinitely dense specs (with a dark event horizon surrounding them) where the gravity is so strong that light enters and cannot escape. Hawking Radiation notwithstanding (hand-waving), not a single one of these proposed monsters has ever been directly observed, and **all** observations of them have turned out to be otherwise: they belch gas, plasma, magnetism, electrons, X-rays, gravity waves, and everything but the kitchen sink.³¹ To complete the lie they release CGI images which alter the data or fabricate it, in order to support the science fiction, while actual radioscope images never show black hole centers.³² See Figures 2-4:

Figure 2 - Artist rendition of supposed black holes;
Corichi/Ruiz

Figure 3 - "This image shows the inner 30 light-years of a dark matter halo in a cluster of young galaxies. The rotating gaseous disk breaks apart into three clumps that collapse under their own gravity to form supermassive stars. Credits: John Wise, Georgia Institute of Technology"³³

Please note the filamentary structures, and the lack of mention of underlying baryonic structure.

²⁹ Ibid. p. 1

³⁰ <https://news.psu.edu/story/552527/2018/12/20/research/beyond-black-hole-singularity>

³¹ <https://www.unige.ch/communication/communiqués/en/2019/le-chaos-ordonne-des-trous-noirs/>

³² [13] & [16]

³³ <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/goddard/2019/birth-of-massive-black-holes-in-the-early-universe-revealed>

Figure 4 - This visualization of a general-relativistic collisionless plasma simulation shows the density of positrons near the event horizon of a rotating black hole. Plasma instabilities produce island-like structures in the region of intense electric current. (Credit: Kyle Parfrey et al./Berkeley Lab)³⁴

Beautiful stuff. The only problem is that black holes are incompatible with WIMPs³⁵ (and DM in general) and besides: **measurements between X-rays and gravity waves (if they are GW), don't agree.**³⁶

³⁴

<https://newscenter.lbl.gov/2019/01/24/how-to-escape-a-black-hole-simulations-provide-new-clues-to-whats-driving-powerful-plasma-jets>

³⁵ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1901.08528.pdf>

³⁶ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1901.03345.pdf>

The author doesn't have a problem with the possibility, as discussed above and in previous parts, that there are large, super-dense, super energetic pinches which drive massive amounts of matter, electromagnetic waves, charges, and "flux ropes" (Birkeland Currents) out into space. This would certainly facilitate the powering of stars, filaments, expansions and contractions (Marklund convection³⁷), flares, repeating novae, pulsars, quasars, AGN, magnetars, etc... The system would require the Void/CRH mechanism discussed above, or a mysteriously infinite aether in a hyperdimensional space oozing into the visible space via some quantum foam or strings, etc... and the author favors the former as it has built in yin-yang recycling entropy and does not violate thermodynamics as the latter might. But at least there is something to power it. Gravitational collapse, whilst being both impossible and nonsensical, violates all of the 5 laws of thermodynamics.³⁸

The figure in (4) being partially edited to *make a black hole* notwithstanding, the article itself reads straight out of PEMC, but a bit *mutated*,

"Parfrey said he realized that more complex simulations to better describe the jets would require a combination of expertise in plasma physics and the general theory of relativity..."

Performed at a supercomputing center at NASA Ames Research Center in Mountain View, California, the simulations incorporate new numerical techniques that provide the first model of a collisionless plasma – in which collisions between charged particles do not play a major role – in the presence of a strong gravitational field associated with a black hole.

The simulations naturally produce effects known as the Blandford-Znajek mechanism³⁹, which describes the twisting magnetic fields that form jets, and a separate Penrose process that describes what happens when negative-energy particles are gulped down by the black hole.⁴⁰

*The Penrose process, "even though it doesn't necessarily contribute that much to extracting the black hole's rotation energy," Parfrey said, "is **possibly directly linked to the electric currents that twist the jets' magnetic fields.**"⁴¹*

*The team intends to better model the process by which **electron-positron pairs**⁴² are created **in the jets** in order to study the jets' plasma distribution and their emission of radiation more realistically for comparison to observations. They also plan to broaden the scope of the simulations to include the flow of infalling matter around the black hole's event horizon, known as its accretion flow."*

In other words: Birkeland Currents, Marklund Convection, and finding the origins of neutrons as pairs. As for accretion, we shall deal with updates on it next. Suffice it to say, this is not passive gravitational accretion, but an active, forceful process they are describing of the stellar and gravitational discs, and it is a major challenge for the SM/BB cosmology to find the energy-mass justification for its formation without an electromagnetic process. Hence the need for the combination of plasma and gravitation by marrying GR with relativistic plasma (measured). But this is a marriage which was said was not needed. For decades GR has been deemed complete, whole, and perfect. But if it is perfect, then why marry it to plasma? Because in the end plasma results can be seen in light bulbs held in hand (see Figure 5), while GR can only be force-fit

³⁷ Marklund, Göran (February 1979). "Plasma convection in force-free magnetic fields as a mechanism for chemical separation in cosmical plasma". *Nature*. **277** (5695): 370–371.

³⁸ [6] & see: Dr. Robitaille's channel, SkyScholar, as well as [126].

³⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Blandford%E2%80%93Znajek_process ; may precede MC but was limited in scope of application. MC describes many scales of plasmoid accumulation which could lead to planets, stars, quasars, pulsars, etc...

⁴⁰ <https://arxiv.org/abs/0804.1912>

⁴¹ <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1977MNRAS.179..433B>

⁴² [16] & [18]

through mathematical interpretation⁴³ and data massaging. E. Dowdye has dealt with this latter issue on his website⁴⁴ and in three presentations.^{45 46 47}

It must be remembered that whatsoever the success of the SM, the fact remains that it is at a confusing and problematic crossroads.⁴⁸

“Particle physics is at a crossroads. The standard model (SM) explains a wide range of phenomena spanning interactions over many orders of magnitude, yet no demonstrated explanation exists for a variety of fundamental questions. Most recently, the discovery of the Higgs boson [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9] at the ATLAS [10] and CMS [11] detectors has addressed the mechanism of electroweak symmetry breaking, but there is no explanation for why the scale of its mass is so much different from naive quantum-mechanical expectations (the “hierarchy problem”) [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], [20]. Dark matter(DM) remains an enigma, despite extensive astronomical confirmation of its existence [21], [22], [23]. Neutrino masses are observed to be nonzero [24], [25], [26], [27], and elements of the Pontecorvo–Maki–Nakagawa–Sakata matrix⁴⁹ [28], [29] have been measured, but these masses are not easily accounted for in the SM [30]. Unification of the strong and electroweak forces is expected, but not yet observed nor understood [31], [32], [33], [34], [35], [36], [37], [38], [39], [40], [41], [42], [43], [44]; such models often predict the existence of yet-to-be-observed leptoquarks (LQs) or proton decay [45]. Furthermore, there are unexpected observations that are not explained in the SM, such as the baryon asymmetry [46], anomalies in the decays of bottom-quark hadrons [47], a discrepancy in the anomalous magnetic moment of the muon ($g-2$) [48], and the strong CP problem [49], [50], [51]. Even further, there are open questions about long-standing observations, such as whether or not there is an extended Higgs sector [52], why there are multiple generations of fermions with a large mass hierarchy [32], [53], [54], [55], and why no magnetic monopoles are observed to exist [56]. For these reasons, the SM is considered to be an effective field theory, and that physics beyond the SM (BSM) should exist.”⁵⁰

Figure 5 - Plasmoids forming in mysterious Vacuum Tube; credit: E. Dollard

A more concise summary that agrees with the author could not be better written or found! The Physics beyond the SM is the Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis as well as Thornhill-Scottian Birkeland Current webs.

⁴³ <http://vixra.org/pdf/1409.0072v9.pdf>

⁴⁴ A condensed analysis of his websites exists in [6], or visit: <https://einsteinwrong.com/site/dr-edward-dowdye/>

⁴⁵ <https://youtu.be/6kJ8gTdOsek>

⁴⁶ <https://youtu.be/CnvOybT2WwU>

⁴⁷ https://youtu.be/B_ixkOI4k8c

⁴⁸ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405428318300121>

⁴⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pontecorvo%E2%80%93Maki%E2%80%93Nakagawa%E2%80%93Sakata_matrix

⁵⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.revip.2018.100027>

Accretion Continues to Dissolve

Accretion Model (AM) has two main issues facing it: (1) electro-cometology⁵¹ and (2) large scale current sheets.

Regarding the second issue, Comerón et al⁵² have this to say,

*“ABSTRACT Thick discs are nearly ubiquitous components of the discs of present-day galaxies. It has been proposed that a fraction of their stars has been accreted. Here, we aim to find whether accretion of satellites is the main thick disc formation mechanism. To do so, we observed a sample of eight nearby edge-on galaxies with the MUSE integral field unit at the VLT. Six of the galaxies have a distinct thick disc. We derived thick disc velocities and velocity dispersions for the galaxies in our sample. We devise a formalism to estimate the fractions of retrograde material in the thick discs by using kinematical maps and thin/thick disc decompositions. None of the galaxies in our sample shows strong evidence for retrograde material at large distances from the centre. Including those found in the literature, there are seventeen thick discs with studied kinematics, with only one showing unambiguous signatures of retrograde material. Literature numerical studies of dynamical friction allow us to estimate that at the current cosmic time about one in six mergers for which the stars of the accreted galaxy ended in a thick disc were retrograde. This is in tension with the observed fraction of 1/17 of galaxies with a partly retrograde thick disc. **We conclude that satellite accretion is not favoured by observations to be the main thick disk formation mechanism.**” (emphasis added)*

“We note that the reported properties of thick discs depend on how thick discs are defined. Indeed, in the Galaxy the thick disc is defined by selecting individual stars based on their kinematics and/or composition”⁵³

It seems to the author that the area of formation is central to cosmology, and so in this way the AM hypothesis is likely to be the most vicious and taciturn area of cosmological upheaval. One would not think so, however the model is both extremely straightforward and “well understood” (by the public) and visible, as well as inextricably tied to gravitation. To challenge accretion is to challenge Einstein and Newton in the minds of the faithful. But, Nature brooks no challenges: she simply barrels through the opposition; go ask SUSY if mother nature slowed down even as she crushed the LHC team at Cern!

So what is Nature suggesting about accretion. As Dr. Robitaille and Wal Thornhill et al... have predicted: it's a total fantasy. Even *if* satellites could and would accrete along the stellar plane, or Saturn's plane (which is only recently now understood precisely enough to debunk accretion ideas⁵⁴), none of the tilts are working in a cohesion to produce the type of single-parent family that is suggested by solar system cosmogenists. Rather, in research into planet 9⁵⁵ and the trans-Neptunian families⁵⁶, it's been found instead that **several** solar orbital planes exist, and in their own families, suggesting separate originations⁵⁷. As

⁵¹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1901.07854.pdf>

⁵² <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1901.10294.pdf>

⁵³ Ibid. p. 2

⁵⁴ <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/news.php?feature=7251>

⁵⁵

<https://www.cam.ac.uk/research/news/mystery-orbits-in-outermost-reaches-of-solar-system-not-caused-by-planet-nine-say-researchers>

⁵⁶ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1809.02571.pdf>

⁵⁷ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.05355.pdf>

discussed previously, even Jupiter’s moons suggest non accretion methods, as you have a pro-grade group, a retro-grade group, and a single moon in that last group going pro-grade!⁵⁸

Nature also has suggested that space is filled with large electrical current sheets⁵⁹, of various thicknesses. Could these mysterious objects⁶⁰ be driving disc formation? They are certainly involved at solar⁶¹ and “micro-scales”.⁶² They have also been implicated at interstellar medium scales.⁶³

Figure 6 - “The electric field forms vortices propagating past two of the Cluster spacecraft. Since the electrons have much lower mass than the ions and can easily be moved around by the electric field, the electrons create a magnetic field, as shown in the bottom panel. (Fig. from Norgren et al., PRL, 2012)”⁶⁴

In the presence of these large structures, is accretion via gravity necessary or tenable? Something tells the author that the SM will *make it so*, and many things that may not necessarily even need each other, just to avoid admitting they didn’t consider

electricity important enough, early enough, or listen to Hannes Alfvén.

Figure 7 - Musca Sheet; “Computer simulation of the Musca cloud, performed at the Metropolis HPC Facility of the Crete Center for Quantum Complexity and Nanotechnology (CCQC) of the University of Crete. The colour scale denotes density of the gas in the cloud. Black lines threading the cloud almost at right angles to its plane are the magnetic field lines.”⁶⁵

⁵⁸ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1809.00700.pdf>

⁵⁹ <https://phys.org/news/2012-08-thin-current-sheets-space-action.html>

⁶⁰ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1811.08563.pdf>

⁶¹

http://articles.adsabs.harvard.edu/cgi-bin/nph-iarticle_query?1988ApJ...326..418S&data_type=PDF_HIGH&whole_paper=YES&type=PRINTER&filetype=.pdf

⁶² <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1711.11284.pdf>

⁶³ <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1086/303824/pdf>

⁶⁴ Ibid.

⁶⁵ <https://www.physics.uoc.gr/en/565958200>

Table 1 :: Proper Physics Chronology⁶⁶

Electricity	Ben Franklin	1751
Gaussian Theory	Carl Gauss	1813
Electromagnetism Unification	Michael Faraday	1831
Doppler Redshift	Hippolyte Fizeau	1848
Maxwell's Equations	James Maxwell	1861-62
Quantized Hypothesis	Ludwig Boltzmann	1877
Photoelectric effect	Heinrich Hertz	1887
Electron Theory	JJ Thomson	1897
Quantum Theory	Max Planck	1900
Relativity theory	Henri Poincare	1900-1904
Mass-energy relation	Henri Poincare	1900
Gravity Waves	Henri Poincare	1905
Special Relativity	Albert Einstein	1905
Photoelectric Effect Explained	Albert Einstein	1905
Birkeland Currents	Kristian Birkeland	1908
Atomic Theory Proved	Ernest Rutherford	1911
Particle-Wave Theory of Atoms and Particles	Niels Bohr	1913
General Relativity	Albert Einstein	1915
Proton discovered	Ernest Rutherford	1919
Quantum Radiation Interaction	Paul Dirac	1920
Quantum Mechanics Codified	Born, Heisenberg, Pauli	1924
Bose-Einstein Condensate	Bose, Einstein	1924
Plasma Cosmology	Irving Langmuir	1927
Big Bang Cosmology	Georges Lemaitre	1927
Missing Matter	Edward Zwicky	1933
Magnetohydrodynamics	Hannes Alfven	1940
QEM/QED	Bethe to Feynman	1947-1960
Electroweak Theory	JC Ward	1959
Quarks	M Gell-Mann & G Zweig	1964
Black Hole Theory	John Wheeler	1967
Dark Matter	Rubin & Ford	1970
Electric Star Theory	Ralph Juergens ⁶⁷	1972
QCD	Gross, Wilczek, & Politzer	1973
Axions	Peicci & Quinn	1977
SUSY	Werner Nahm	1978
WIMPs	unclear ⁶⁸	1980
MOND	Mordehai Milgrom	1982
String Theory	Green & Schwarz	1984
Dark Energy	Friedman ⁶⁹ or Sivaram ⁷⁰	1924 or 1986
M Theory	Edward Witten	1995
Intrinsic Redshift	Halton Arp ⁷¹	1998

⁶⁶ Tables 1 and 2 reproduced from [11]; all references in [18] included, as this paper is a follow-up.

⁶⁷ https://www.velikovsky.info/Ralph_Juergens

⁶⁸ <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/dark-matter-exotic-possibilities/>

⁶⁹ <http://home.fnal.gov/~skent/early.html>

⁷⁰ <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/0809/0809.3364.pdf>

⁷¹ https://www.haltonarp.com/articles/intrinsic_redshifts_in_quasars_and_galaxies.pdf

Table 2 :: Falsifications

Cosmic Background Radiation	2007 ⁷⁴ & 2019 ⁷⁵
ΛCDM	2010 ⁷⁶ , 2014 ⁷⁷
SUSY	2012 ⁷⁸ - 2017 ⁷⁹
CDM	2012 ⁸⁰ , 2015 ⁸¹ , 2016 ⁸² - 2018 ^{83 84 85 86}
WIMPs & MACHOs	2017 ⁸⁷
Galaxy Rotation and DM	2017 ^{88 89}
Standard Redshift	2017 ^{90 91 92}
MOND	2018 ^{93 94 95}
Galaxy Rotation and MOND	2018 ⁹⁶
Higgs-boson as non-standard Quark	2018 ⁹⁷
Dark Energy	2018 ⁹⁸
LDM	2018 ^{99 100}
Classical Black Holes	2018 ¹⁰¹
Accretion Model	2019 ¹⁰²

⁷² <http://www.astro.caltech.edu/~george/ay20/ea-wimps-machos.pdf>

⁷³ <https://theconversation.com/from-machos-to-wimps-meet-the-top-five-candidates-for-dark-matter-51516>

⁷⁴ <http://rnas.asj-oa.am/2542/1/73.pdf>

⁷⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p8IKQMEYYLw>

⁷⁶ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1011.0004>

⁷⁷ https://astro.uni-bonn.de/~pavel/kroupa_SciLogs.html

⁷⁸ <http://backreaction.blogspot.com/2016/08/the-lhc-nightmare-scenario-has-come-true.html>

⁷⁹ <https://www.space.com/39001-dark-matter-doesnt-exist-study-suggests.html>

⁸⁰ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1204.2546>

⁸¹ http://adsabs.harvard.edu/cgi-bin/bib_query?arXiv:1406.4860

⁸² <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2016arXiv161003854K>

⁸³ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.09823.pdf>

⁸⁴ <https://academic.oup.com/mnras/article/476/3/3124/4875952>

⁸⁵ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1807.07113.pdf>

⁸⁶ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.04817.pdf>

⁸⁷ <https://phys.org/news/2017-12-machos-dead-wimps-no-showsay-simps.html>

⁸⁸ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.10706.pdf>

⁸⁹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1811.08843.pdf>

⁹⁰ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.03298.pdf>

⁹¹ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1807.09409>

⁹² <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.03888.pdf>

⁹³ <https://www.physicsforums.com/threads/falsifications-and-constraints-due-to-gw-measurements.929254/>

⁹⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.04167.pdf>

⁹⁵ <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1809/1809.09019.pdf>

⁹⁶ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1801.09304.pdf>

⁹⁷ <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-06130-9>

⁹⁸ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.05027.pdf>

⁹⁹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.10543.pdf>

¹⁰⁰ Several, see previous papers to the series

¹⁰¹ Ibid.

¹⁰² Ibid.

Conclusion

The continual search for the Dark Universe is taking a predictably droll turn wherein the surety of finding said matter (predicted with *a priori* knowledge) demands replacements. The replacements are manifold and yet not connected via anything real, except the electrical connections documented or found in these collaborative experiments. On occasion new discoveries are made which support the plasma model, but otherwise, all of the proposed DU hypotheses constrain out, and are replaced with electrical hypotheses, or pseudoscientific unicorns. Meanwhile Black Holes and Accretion continue to simplify nicely into current-based models.

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